

HOW TO REMOVE HESITATION WHILE SPEAKING IN ENGLISH?

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Annotation. *In the process of speaking in English, it is important to have sufficient pronunciation, fluency, vocabulary and to be able to speak without any hesitations. There are people among us who have some fear or excitement while speaking. In this article, We will try to consider the causes of hesitation, in what situations it occurs and ways to prevent it.*

Keywords: *hesitation, speaking, pause, speech, causes of hesitation, vocabulary, communication, personal level, conflict resolution, personal growth, professional advancement.*

First of all, the person speaking should be able to attract attention, the speech should be worthy of people's attention, and the tone of the speech should be enviable. And at this time, our confidence and knowledge may not always be enough. Well, hesitation is the act of pausing before doing something. A *hesitation* is a pause. If your friend asks you, "Do you like my new haircut?" you'd better make sure there's not a second's *hesitation* before you answer, "Yes, of course!" Hesitation happens when you feel uncertainty or doubt. It can be a pause in speech, a faltering moment before you act, or a silent second of indecision. If your friend's dog is growling and staring you down, but she tells you he won't bite, that feeling that something not feeling right that stops you from petting him is hesitation. The Latin root of *hesitation* is *haesitationem*, which means irresolution or uncertainty. Let's try to look some causes of hesitation. It is important to know what makes you tongue tied in a situation you should be speaking up. Hesitation can happen due to many reasons, we have grouped them into following basic categories:

1. Hesitation due to lack of knowledge: Obviously, you cannot talk about something you do not know. You also cannot use a tool you don't understand. Similarly, if you are asked to speak about something that you do not have enough information about, you will not be able to speak well. Similarly, if you lack basic knowledge of grammar or your vocabulary is very small or you have insufficient exposure to English, you will hesitate.

2. Hesitation due to lack of skills: There is another form of hesitation too – one that happens due to lack of skills. Whenever you feel like you can write good English and read and understand it but hesitate to speak, because you lack speaking skills.

Whenever you feel like you know everything about something but still hesitate to do it, then that hesitation is caused by lack of skills. The detrimental effects of hesitation in communication can have significant consequences in various aspects of our lives. Whether in professional or personal settings, hesitation can lead to missed opportunities and the erosion of relationships. By recognizing the impact of hesitation and actively working to overcome it, we can enhance our communication skills and improve our overall success.

In professional settings, hesitation can hinder career advancement and limit networking opportunities: when we hesitate to communicate our goals, aspirations, and achievements, we risk being overlooked by employers and missing out on promotions. By not expressing our desires for growth and recognition, we fail to position ourselves as valuable assets within the organization. In contrast, colleagues who are open and assertive about their ambitions often receive the recognition and opportunities they seek. Similarly, hesitation in networking and forming partnerships can

restrict our professional growth. Building professional networks and seeking collaborations require effective communication and a proactive approach. By hesitating to reach out to potential collaborators, attend industry events, or initiate conversations, we limit our exposure to new opportunities and restrict the growth of our networks. Proactive communication is crucial in creating meaningful connections that can lead to future collaborations, career advancements, and knowledge exchange.

On a personal level, hesitation can strain relationships and turn once-favourite individuals into strangers: when we hesitate to assert ourselves and communicate our needs, concerns, or dissatisfaction, we allow others to make assumptions or take advantage of us, creating imbalances in relationships and causing emotional distress. Furthermore, hesitation in expressing emotions and vulnerabilities can contribute to emotional distance in relationships. By hesitating to share our feelings, fears, or desires, we miss opportunities for deeper connections with our loved ones. Open and honest communication is crucial for maintaining intimacy and understanding. When we hesitate to express ourselves, we create barriers that hinder emotional growth and may ultimately result in the loss of connection.

Personal Growth: Assertiveness plays a pivotal role in personal development. By cultivating assertiveness, individuals gain the confidence to voice their opinions, assert their boundaries, and stand up for their rights. For instance, imagine a person who has always been hesitant to express their true feelings in a romantic relationship. By developing assertiveness, they can communicate their needs, desires, and concerns effectively, fostering healthier and more fulfilling connections.

Professional Advancement: In the realm of career growth, assertiveness is a valuable asset. Those who can confidently articulate their ideas, provide constructive feedback, and negotiate for their interests are more likely to excel in their professional endeavours. Consider an employee who is hesitant to speak up during team meetings. By cultivating assertiveness, they can actively contribute to discussions, showcase their expertise, and potentially influence decisions, leading to career advancement opportunities.

Conflict Resolution: Assertiveness plays a crucial role in resolving conflicts and maintaining healthy relationships. When individuals are assertive, they can express their perspectives and concerns calmly and respectfully, without being overly passive or aggressive. This approach encourages open dialogue, promotes understanding, and helps find mutually beneficial solutions. For example, in a collaborative project where team members have differing opinions, assertiveness allows each person to contribute their ideas while respecting others' viewpoints, leading to effective problem-solving. Moreover, the present study was conceived as an investigation of the hypothesis that hesitation in spontaneous speech are attributable to the difficulty in selecting the word immediately following hesitation, and the implication that the difficulty of selection is directly related to the relative frequency of the word to be selected. It seemed worthwhile to devote some attention to the possibility that hesitation phenomena are even more directly related to the cognitive complexity of the utterance within which they occur. It worth emphasizing that speaking is a productive part of the language learning process. Speaking will be important for students in their daily life, for example: describing something, complaining to other and making conversation with foreign as the tool of commerce. Nunan in Juniardi stated One essential component of learning a foreign language is being fluent in speaking, and success is determined by how well one can carry on a conversation in that language. By mastering speaking skill students will be able to communicate to each other to build a good interaction. Students

frequently made mistakes when making speech. Students will occasionally pause, repeats, false start and restart in the middle of a statement to choose the right words to say next. The students frequently do not know the language that students should have used when answering questions from lectures in class discussion or when presenting particular theme in front of the class. This characteristic of phenomenon known as hesitation.

Removing hesitation: now how do you remove hesitation? It is simple enough. We summarize success strategies for hesitation removal as follows. Back yourself up and commit to the following plan and you will see your hesitation break and then slowly disappear. Building good English speaking skills without hesitation is a life long mission – you need to keep sharpening the edge, however, with the combination of the approaches given below, you will be able to quickly achieve dramatic reduction in your hesitation and also be on your way to the state of fluent and confident English for life.

Everyone of you needs the long term solution. Those of you who have an interview coming up or an important client meeting, should also take up short term approach along with the long term one.

Hesitation elimination through practice:

- Time for results to show up: 1-3 months;
- We are afraid of doing something which we have not done before or not done many times;
- We hesitate to drive on the highway if we have not driven on the highway before;
- We fear talking to girls if we haven't talked to many girls before;
- We hesitate to perform on a stage if we haven't participated in many dramas or plays before.

The same with English speaking: the fear will be all gone when you have already spoken in English many times; Yes, the only long term solution is to practice speaking in English. Find a friend, find a colleague, find a spoken English partner or join a conversation based training program. Find any method that works for you but give yourself your daily dose of English speaking practice if you want to kill the fear monster forever.

Quick trick to defeat hesitation: long term solution is like Yoga. If you do *pranayam* everyday, you'll live longer and healthier. Similarly, if you practice English speaking with a partner, friend, colleague or a trainer everyday – it will build your confidence on solid foundation.

In conclusion, hesitation in communication can have far-reaching consequences. It can lead to missed opportunities for career growth, limit networking possibilities, strain relationships, and create emotional distance. By overcoming hesitation and actively practising assertiveness, we can enhance our communication skills, seize opportunities, nurture relationships, and ultimately achieve personal and professional success. Practice English speaking daily with a friend, partner, colleague or a trainer everyday like a yoga practitioner. To hell with grammar. Speak wrong English if you have to, but do not sit silent like a boiled egg. It is worth mentioning that setting specific goals plays crucial role. If you know you have trouble running more than a mile, start with what you can do. What exactly do I want to achieve with this infographic? Reveal hidden trends and patterns using data. Break down complex information and present it in an easy-to-digest way. Provide your audience with a step-by-step guide on how to do something. Raise awareness of a specific issue or cause. Create a comprehensive, go-to visual resource on a topic. Compare two or more products or concepts. Translate a story, such as a brand story, into a timeline infographic. Each of these different goals corresponds to a different type of infographic, so choose which one best fits your needs at the moment and consult chapter 3 of the complete e-book (download for

free above) to determine the best format for your message. Make sure your goal is measurable and achievable. Make sure that you move forward with your progress and take steps that get done in sequence to reach your destination. Your goal must have a deadline. Your deadline should motivate you and should be realistic. In terms of weight loss, a goal of one to two pounds per week is realistic. In terms of body fat, that translates to about a half a percent per week. You've accomplished something, now give yourself some praise for it. It's good to tell yourself you did a good job, even if you only met part of your goal.

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